

RECIPES OF BASIC FOODS AND TECHNOLOGY OF THEIR PREPARATION FOR YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation: Nowadays, most of the main foods that are given to children are non-natural products. In this article, we have developed a recipe aimed at the composition of complementary foods mainly for young children, consisting of completely natural products.

Key words: natural foods, preparation of a gruel, semolina, milk, butter, sugar juice, solution of NaCl, potato, cabbage, parsley, carrot.

1. Gruel (8%) prepared in diluted milk (proportion 1:1)

table 1

No	Name of products	Intended norm
1	semolina	8 g
2	milk	50 ml
3	water	60 ml
4	solution of NaCl	1.5 ml
5	sugar juice	5 ml
6	butter	3 g

2. Gruel (8%) prepared in diluted milk (proportion 2:1)

table 2

No	Name of products	Intended norm
1	semolina	8 g
2	milk	67 ml
3	water	43 ml
4	solution of NaCl	1.5 ml
5	sugar juice	5 ml
6	butter	3 g

Preparation mode. Sift the semolina with a sieve, put a little in boiling water and boil 15-20 minutes, stirring. Then the milk is mixed and brought to a boil, heated until a steam appears, put in the prepared gruel. Butter is added to sugar juice, mixed and put out on clean bottles, which are sterilized(table 1,2).

3. Gruel (10%) prepared in vegetable bouillon

table 3

No	Name of products	Intended norm
1	potato	30 g
2	cabbage	30 g
3	carrot	20 g
4	parsley (root)	3 g
5	semolina	10 g
6	solution of NaCl	2 ml
7	butter	5 g
8	water	200 ml

Preparation mode. Wash and then cut the potatoes, cabbage, carrot, parsley(root). Put them in boiling water in 20-25 minutes and add solution of NaCl. After, add to mixture and mix them(table 3).

4. Gruel (10%) prepared in meat bouillon

table 4

No	Name of products	Intended norm
1	meat	40 g
2	semolina	10 g
3	solution of NaCl	2 ml
4	Parsley(root)	3 g
5	butter	3 g
6	water	200 ml

Preparation mode. Firstly, wash and cut the meat and parsley and then boil them in hot water until the bouillon prepared. Add a semolina to water and mix them with a bouillon, butter(table 4).

5. Puree-soup prepared vegetables

table 5

No	Name of products	Intended norm
1	potato	20 g
2	cabbage	10 g
3	carrot	10 g
4	Parsley(root)	5 g
5	butter	3 g
6	water	60 ml
7	solution of NaCl	2 ml
8	onion	5 g
9	peas	4 g
10	rice	10 g
11	cream(10%)	10 ml
12	yolk	2 pc

Preparation mode. Cut and fry the onion in the butter. All vegetables are cut and fry with an onion together. Make a rice bouillon adding some water. Then add rice bouillon, cooked yolk to mixture and mix them(table 5).

6. Preparation mode of curd

Boiled, baked and cooled to a temperature of about 60°C , half a liter of milk is cleaned and washed, then poured into a glass with boiling water. A sachet is put in the milk, the mouth of the dish is poured and stored in a warm place. After 1.5-2 hours, the milk is mixed and left for 16-18 hours at the temperature itself. Cool the curd to 8-10°C heat and store for a day.

Used for the preparation of curd, the dropper is sold in the form of droppers, which have microbes that absorb milk. You can also use yogurt itself in place of drops. In 10-12 hours, it will bring the milk to a liquid state at home temperature.

7. Kissel of black currant

table 6

No	Name of products	Intended norm
1	dried black currant	8 g
2	sugar juice	15 ml
3	Potato flour	4 g
4	water	100 ml

Preparation mode. Black currant peel, wash and pour cold water on top and leave for a day in a container. Then it is brought to a boil with a spoon inside and passed through two layers of gauze. Sugar juice, potato flour is added to the boiling water and poured into bottles.

8. Kissel of blueberries

table 7

№	Name of products	Intended norm
1	dried blueberries	8 g
2	sugar juice	15 ml
3	Potato flour	4 g
4	water	100 ml

Preparation mode. Blueberries peel, wash and pour cold water on top and leave for a day in a container. Then it is brought to a boil with a spoon inside and passed through two layers of gauze. Sugar juice, potato flour is added to the boiling water and poured into bottles.

9. Kissel of briars

table 8

№	Name of products	Intended norm
1	dried briars	8 g
2	sugar juice	15 ml
3	Potato flour	4 g
4	water	100 ml

Preparation mode. Briars peel, wash and pour cold water on top and leave for a day in a container. Then it is brought to a boil with a spoon inside and passed through two layers of gauze. Sugar juice, potato flour is added to the boiling water and poured into bottles.

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